

GraphNEx - Data Management

Version 0

Description

GraphNEx contributes a graph-based framework for developing inherently explainable AI.

Unlike current AI systems that utilise complex networks to learn high-dimensional, abstract representations of data, GraphNEx embeds symbolic meaning within AI frameworks. We will combine semantic reasoning over knowledge bases with simple modular learning on new data observations, to adaptively evolve the graphical knowledge base. The core concept is to decompose the monolithic block of highly connected layers of deep learning architectures into many smaller, simpler units. Units perform a precise task with an interpretable output, associating a value or vector to nodes. Nodes will be connected depending on their (learned) similarity, correlation in the data or closeness in some space.

GraphNEx will employ the concepts and tools from graph signal processing and graph machine learning to extrapolate semantic concepts and meaningful relationships from sub-graphs (concepts) within the knowledge base that can be used for semantic reasoning. By enforcing sparsity and domain-specific priors between concepts we will promote human interpretability.

The integration of game-based user feedback will ensure that explanations (and therefore core mechanisms of the AI system) are understandable and relevant to humans.

GraphNEx validates the framework with two applicative scenarios in which transparency and trust are critical:

- Privacy Protection to safeguard personal information from unwanted non-essential inferences from multimedia data (images, video and audio) as well as to support informed consent.

System Genetics to assist the discovery of clinically and biologically relevant concepts on large, multimodal genetic and genomic datasets; and

Funder

CHIST-ERA||CHIST-ERA

Grant

GraphNEx: Graph Neural Networks for Explainable Artificial Intelligence/ No EP/V062107/1

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Organizations

École Normale Supérieure de Lyon, École Polytechnique
Fédérale de Lausanne, Queen Mary University of London

1. Basic Information

Title: GraphNEx - Data Management

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2. License

License: CC0-1.0

Access Rights: Public

3. Funding

Funder: CHIST-ERA|CHIST-ERA

Grant: GraphNEx: Graph Neural Networks for Explainable Artificial Intelligence

4. Data Management

Descriptions

Multimedia data for Privacy Protection

Publicly available datasets are used to assist the discovery of privacy concepts and associated privacy risks in image, video and audio data, to safeguard personal information from unwanted non-essential inferences, and to support informed consent. Derived data, for example, in the form of graph and audio-visual features, and newly collected data will be also included.

Template: [CHIST-ERA Data Management](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 What data (for example the kind, formats, and volumes), will be collected or produced?

1.1.1 Give details on the kind of data

- Observational (e.g.
 - sensor data
 - data from surveys)
- Derived or compiled (e.g.
 - text mining
 - 3D models)
- Reference or canonical (e.g.
 - static
 - peer-reviewed data sets
 - likely published or curated
 - such as gene sequence databanks or chemical structures)

1.1.2 Give details on the data format

Multimedia data for Privacy Protection includes images, videos, and audio files, and their transformation into graph format to be used in the graph-based framework of GraphNEx. Portable Network Graphics (PNG) is the preferred format for images, as it supports lossless data compression. Waveform Audio File Format (WAV) is the preferred format for storing audio files. MPEG-4 is the preferred container format for video data (.mp4). These data can be accompanied by annotations in CSV and JSON formats as open standards. Some of the data, for example when re-using existing public dataset or for storage size and sharing purposes, can be available in different formats and compression of those mentioned here.

1.1.3 Justify the use of certain formats

de facto standard in my discipline

1.1.4 Give details on the volumes

GB (gigabyte)

Publicly available datasets for images, audios, and videos can occupy from thousands to hundred of thousands of GBs. For example, PrivacyAlert contains 6,000 images occupying about 1 GB. VISPR has ~22,000, occupying ~50 GBs. Audioset is an audio event dataset that consists of ~2.1 million human-annotated 10-second video clips collected from YouTube. Kinetics-700 is a video dataset of 650,000 clips that covers 700 human action classes, occupying ~700 GB.

1.2 How will new data be collected or produced?

1.2.1 Explain which methodologies or software will be used if new data are collected or produced or if third party data are used

No new multimedia data has been collected. We re-used and transformed existing and publicly available datasets.

1.2.2 Explain how data provenance will be documented

Location of the re-used datasets will be provided as link in the GitHub repositories published by GraphNEx and associated with peer-reviewed

publications. For individual data, such as images of a dataset linked to their original source from social media like Flickr or YouTube, we will also provide tabular or textual files with the links to the original source, license, and any change in their status (e.g., no longer available).

2.1.1 What metadata and documentation will accompany the data?

2.1.1.1 Indicate which metadata will be provided to help others identify and discover the data

Descriptive

2.1.1.2 Indicate which metadata standards will be used

- OpenAIRE Guidelines
- DataCite Metadata Schema

2.1.1.3 Indicate how the data will be organised during the project

As the original dataset was not organised following any conventions, we re-organised the structure of the dataset to provide an easier way to access and re-use the data. For example, all the annotations are grouped into a single folder and instead of using separate .csv files for each data split, we use a single annotation file with the data splits annotated as additional columns of the file. Images are stored in a separate folder and grouped in chunks of 1000 images for each sub-directory to ease the visualisation to a user when using a file explorer (e.g., from a server). We provide an additional folder with bash scripts for Linux systems to re-organise the original dataset into the provided format.

2.1.1.4 Consider what other documentation is needed to enable re-use

GraphNEx will provide a README file in Markdown or textual format to document the organisation of the data, and any script or tool used to re-organise and transform the raw data. If new software will be developed to transform the data or read the transformed and re-organised data, GraphNEx will provide the link to the GitHub repository made publicly available.

2.1.1.5 Consider how this information will be captured and where it will be recorded

readme text file (Markdown format)

2.1.2 What data quality control measures will be used?

2.1.2.1 Explain how the consistency and quality of data collection will be controlled and documented

Peer review of data

Data will be used across partners and team members, as well as used for the training of various machine learning models. This re-use of the data will provide the peer-review process to ensure the consistency and quality, and document any issue and how it was addressed. For example, for images no longer available on the social media, we update the annotation file to include a negative number in the data split column. This solution makes the data loader ignoring the image and its annotation for any subsequent task (e.g., training of the model, computation of performance measures).

3.1 Reused Data

3.1.1 How will existing data be re-used?

- To reproduce and validate findings
- To compare and combine with other data
- To follow-up research on a specific area
- To develop new products/ services
- To contribute to the wider community (researchers
- public authorities
- citizen scientists)

Not applicable

3.1.2 Where can re-used data be found?

Zenodo; website of the dataset authors

3.1.3 Which data will be re-used?

[PrivacyAlert: a dataset for image privacy prediction](#)

- PrivacyAlert, Version v2, <https://zenodo.org/records/6406870>

- PicAlert!, <http://l3s.de/picalert/> (webpage no longer available), copy of the archive by other researchers
- VISPR, <https://tribhuvanesh.github.io/vpa/>
- Visual Redactions, <https://resources.mpi-inf.mpg.de/d2/orekondy/redactions/>
- PA-HMDB51, <https://htwang14.github.io/PA-HMDB51-website/index.html>
- VizWiz-Priv, <https://vizwiz.org/>

3.1.4 State any constraints on re-use of existing data if there are any

No constraint. However, some of the original images might have been deleted by the users from Flickr and/or their license might have been changed since the compilation of the dataset was originally done.

3.1.5 Briefly state the reasons if the re-use of any existing data sources has been considered but discarded

Not applicable

4.1.1 How will data and metadata be stored and backed up during the research?

4.1.1.1 Describe where the data will be stored and backed up during research activities and how often the backup will be performed

Daily

GraphNEx will guarantee the long-term sustainability of its data with last generation backup systems within each institution, e.g. IT service, and via the service provided by GitHub. The IT service of QMUL will provide regular, over-night backups of the server where the GraphNEx website is hosted. QMUL is partnering with Microsoft for the cloud hosting, sharing and backup of institutional data, for example using OneDrive. QMUL in collaboration with GitHub, also provides the GitHub Enterprise service and therefore all data can be hosted, backed up, and tracked the versions within QMUL.

Copy of the data can also be stored in other institutional workstations provided to the members of the project for data inspection, visualisation, and processing.

4.1.2 How will data security and protection of sensitive data be taken care of during the research?

4.1.2.1 Explain how the data will be recovered in the event of an incident

The use of publicly available datasets, the servers managed by the institution IT service, and repository platform such as Zenodo and GitHub, allows the recovery of the data in case of any incident. Multiple backups and shared access also enable the recovery.

4.1.2.2 Explain who will have access to the data during the research and how access to data is controlled, especially in collaborative partnerships

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Myriam Bontonou, ENS de Lyon

4.1.2.3 Describe the main risks and how these will be managed

GraphNEx uses publicly available datasets according to their license. However, the partners can interact with users for testing the explainability of the models, the multimedia data of users and the feedback from users for evaluating the new concept graphs developed in the project. The partners will seek the explicit consent of the users (opt-in model) before storing or processing the data belonging to the users. The individuals will be able to

withdraw their consent at any time, in which case their data will permanently be erased. No identifiable information will be captured from participants.

4.1.2.4 Explain which institutional data protection policies are in place

Queen Mary University London

<https://www.qmul.ac.uk/privacy/media/arcs/policyzone/Data-Protection-Policy-v03.1.pdf>

5.1.1 Personal data

5.1.1.1 Are there any personal data to be formulated?

No

5.1.2.1 Data ownership and accessibility

5.1.2.1.1 Who will be the owner(s) of the data?

Queen Mary University of London

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- Emmanouil Benetos (orcid: [0000-0002-6820-6764](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6820-6764))

5.1.2.1.2 Explain what access will apply to the data?

- Open
- Embargoed

GraphNEx will mostly re-use existing and publicly available datasets. Enriched metadata, reorganization of the existing data, and transformed data will be still make openly available. Some of the data could be under embargoed until the associated manuscript has been peer-reviewed and published. When interacting with users, no identifiable information will be captured from participants.

5.1.2.2 Intellectual property rights

5.1.2.2.1 Explain which intellectual property and how will they be dealt with

Other

The GraphNEx Consortium Agreement (CA) is based on the DESCAs model (<https://www.desca-agreement.eu/desca-model-consortium-agreement/>). This CA addresses the rights and obligations of each partner regarding confidentiality, the definition of the background knowledge brought by each participant and related access rights, rules to be applied for joint ownership, access rights to the project results for the partners and for third parties. Each participating organisation will declare any IP brought into the project or to be developed within it. Participants will be given the opportunity to raise objections against such a declaration and such objections will be promptly dealt with by the Project Management Committee.

5.1.2.3 Third-party data restrictions

5.1.2.3.1 Are there any restrictions on the re-use of third-party data?

No

5.1.3 Ethical issues

5.1.3.1 What ethical issues and codes of conduct are there, and how will they be taken into account?

Ethical issues surrounding personal data

Project partners are committed to the highest ethical standards by conforming to the relevant national and European legislations, including the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The partners also embrace the AREA framework (Anticipate, Reflect, Engage and Act) and will develop common best practice guidelines for users interacting with learnable systems using machine learning on user data and user input, with due consideration of ethical and societal impacts of the technology.

Ethical issues may arise with user interaction for testing the explainability of the models, the genomic data, the multimedia data of users and the feedback from users for evaluating the new concept graphs developed in the project, as well as in the two use-cases. The partners will seek the explicit

consent of the users (opt-in model) before processing the data. Moreover, the individuals will be able to withdraw their consent at any time, in which case their data will permanently be erased. Video and audio recordings will be stored in the computing servers of QMUL, and will be only accessible to personnel associated with the project; no dual-use of the data will be allowed and the system to be used has already been approved to process these data. Data in the servers will be maintained after the project ends and will be managed according to the current regulations and their future updates. Participants that will evaluate the explainability of the models will provide their informed consent. Their participation will be voluntary, and can withdraw at any stage. No identifiable information will be captured from participants.

All research Work Packages will be subject to oversight by the Ethics committees of the partner institutions. The coordinator will be supported by Hazel Covill, the Ethics Facilitator at QMUL, and will obtain approval from the QMUL Ethical Committee prior to any data collections. The coordinator will also be liaising through the local PIs with the Data Protection Officer and Ethical Committees at ENSL and EPFL.

Ethics related to the use of datasets for training neural networks will be regularly discussed with all the participants. The participants are concerned with the possible biases that could influence the results of the machine learning process. However, since the focus is on explainable AI, biases should be identified more easily than with a standard ML.

6.1.1 How and when will data be shared? Are there possible restrictions to data sharing or embargo reasons?

6.1.1.1 Explain how the data will be discoverable and shared

- Deposit in a trustworthy data repository
- Direct handling of data requests

6.1.1.2 Outline the plan for data preservation and give information on how long the data will be retained

Datasets and use-cases will be kept under version control, and released on public repositories (e.g. Zenodo) as standalone projects encapsulating data, code, documentation and, when applicable, system requirements in the form of a Docker image. Models and research datasets will normally be made available under Creative Commons licenses, except where forbidden by copyright restrictions. All the shared datasets and documents will have a Digital Object Identifier. Research data will be backed up and archived. QMUL data management policies ensure long-term preservation of data for 10 years beyond the end of the project.

6.1.1.3 Explain when the data will be made available

Part of the data and corresponding tools are made openly and publicly available once associated peer-reviewed manuscripts are accepted for publications to a conference or journal. Some of the data has been already made available, whereas re-used datasets are already publicly available.

6.1.1.5 Will exclusive use of the data be claimed?

No

6.1.1.7 Indicate whether data sharing will be embargoed or restricted

Embargoed

Curated publicly available datasets and derived data from them, e.g. in the format of graph data, can remain under an embargo period until the associated manuscript is peer-reviewed and accepted for publications.

6.1.1.8 Indicate who will be able to use the data

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Education
- The public
- Industry

6.1.1.9 Is it necessary to restrict access to certain communities or to apply a data sharing agreement?

No

6.1.2 How will data for preservation be selected, and where data will be preserved long-term?

6.1.2.1 Indicate what data must be retained or destroyed for contractual, legal, or regulatory purposes

Retained

Curated data and transformed data in graph format.

6.1.2.2 Indicate how it will be decided what data to keep

GraphNEx follows the institutional data retention policy and the potential re-usability of the data by community.

6.1.2.3 Describe the data to be preserved long-term

- Observational (e.g.
 - sensor data
 - data from surveys)
- Derived or compiled (e.g.
 - text mining
 - 3D models)
- Reference or canonical (e.g.
 - static
 - peer-reviewed data sets
 - likely published or curated
 - such as gene sequence databanks or chemical structures)

6.1.2.4 Explain the foreseeable research uses (and/ or users) for the data

Curated and transformed multimedia data for the privacy protection use case will be important for the research community to develop novel machine learning models and compare performance results in a fairer and reproducible set up.

6.1.2.5 Indicate where the data will be deposited

Zenodo, GitHub

6.1.2.6 Demonstrate that the data can be curated effectively beyond the lifetime of the grant

Queen Mary University of London:

- <https://www.qmul.ac.uk/governance-and-legal-services/media/arcs/policyzone/Records-Retention-Policy-2010-v01.4.pdf>
- <https://www.qmul.ac.uk/governance-and-legal-services/governance/information-governance/records-management/records-retention-schedule/>

Zenodo: <https://about.zenodo.org/policies/>

GitHub: <https://docs.github.com/en/repositories/archiving-a-github-repository/about-archiving-content-and-data-on-github>

6.1.3 What methods or software tools are needed to access and use data?

6.1.3.1 Indicate how the data will be shared

Repository

6.1.4 How will the application of a unique and persistent identifier to each data set be ensured?

6.1.4.1 Select how the data might be re-used in other contexts

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To develop a product
- To improve a product
- To combine with other data
- To contribute to the wider community (researchers
- public authorities
- citizen scientists)

6.1.4.2 What type of persistent identifier (PID) will be used?

DOI

7.1.1 Who will be responsible for data management?

7.1.1.1 Outline the roles and responsibilities for data management/stewardship activities

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data sharing

7.1.1.2 Explain the co-ordination of data management responsibilities across partners

QMUL will be the main responsible for the data management of these data. QMUL will share with the other partners the tools (software) to access and process the data and the password-protected archives of the data (if not yet publicly available).

7.1.2 What resources will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable)?

7.1.2.1 Explain how the necessary resources to prepare the data for sharing/preservation have been costed in

- Use of institution infrastructure
- Other

Use of GitHub and Zenodo

7.1.2.2 Indicate whether additional resources will be needed to prepare data for deposit or to meet any charges from data repositories

Yes

7.1.2.3 Explain how much cost provisionally is needed

Pound Sterling

150/TB

Data preservation costs at QMUL, after the first free 1TB are costed at GBP 150/TB/year. Costs have been included in the financial plan of the project.

5. Software Management

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